

Competitive Intelligence

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Today the competition is so strong that the most visionary organizations have realized that the real race is in the future, and follows a cycle of birth, youth, maturity, decline and eventually death.

To prevent decline, the company needs permanently seek a new life cycle curve, a transformational leap that enables a new development cycle.

The set of methods and techniques for monitoring the external and competitive environment are proposed by the area of competitive intelligence (CI). These methods bring together a set of information processing and analysis procedures, through which the company develops what is called "preventive" listening to the environment.

Often such monitoring only identifies trends, e.g. "weak signals" from the environment, that have the creative aim of uncovering opportunities and reducing risks linked to uncertainty.

Competitive intelligence systems are intended to provide companies with a systematic program for collecting, processing, analyzing and disseminating information about competitors' activities, technologies and overall business trends in order to achieve corporate goals.

Marketing intelligence "is market knowledge, so that you can minimize the uncertainties inherent in decisions in organizations and minimize the risk of a wrong decision".

Concepts and Definitions

Competitive Intelligence has also been treated as Business Intelligence, Marketing Intelligence and Strategic Knowledge Management; in the United States as Technology Watch, Competitive Intelligence System, Business Intelligence, Competitor Intelligence; and in France, "Veille Technologique", "Intelligence Economique", "Intelligence Concurrentielle".

- Competitive Intelligence is a systematic institutional program for mining and analyzing information about competitor activities and trends in the specific sector and the market in general, with the purpose of leading the organization to achieve its objectives and goals;

- It is a strategic information management activity that aims to enable decision makers to anticipate market trends and competition developments, detect and assess threats and opportunities in their environment to define offensive actions and defensive products better suited to the company's development
- Process of collecting, analyzing and disseminating relevant, specific intelligence, at the appropriate time, regarding the implications for the business environment, competitors and the organization;
- Information that assures the decision maker that the company is still competitive ... intelligence is the watchdog of competitiveness, not a passive connoisseur of competitors ... Competitive intelligence or business intelligence is a tool of the company leader, a core competency that results from a broad view of the company toward its competitor, which seeks to ceaselessly exploit its weaknesses while frustrating competitive surprises. It is optimally placed in the context of the strategic goal to displace the best or remain the best in an industrial segment;
- Systematic process of collecting, processing, analyzing and disseminating information about competitors' activities, technologies and general business trends, in order to support decision making and achieve the company's strategic goals.

Competitive intelligence is a proactive information process that leads to better decision making, whether strategic or operational. It is also considered as a systematic process aimed at uncovering the governing forces of business, reducing risk and leading the decision maker to act in advance, as well as protecting the knowledge generated.

The information process is composed of the stages of collection and ethical search of data, reports and formal and informal information (from the macro environment as well as from the company's competitive and internal environment), analysis of filtered and integrated form and its dissemination.

Therefore, it can be summarized that Competitive Intelligence refers to the set of monitoring and analysis activities of environmental data, structures and processes with the purpose of providing useful information to decision making and strategic business planning.

The concepts of systems underlie the field of information systems, thus the generic concepts of systems apply to companies and to the components and activities of information systems. The most common system concepts are those in which:

- Computer networks are component information processing systems;
- the uses of computer networks by companies are actually interconnected information systems;

- Developing ways to use computer networks in business includes designing the basic components of information systems;
- Information technology management emphasizes the quality, business value, and security of an organization's information systems.

IS contains information about people, places, and things of interest, in the environment around the organization, and within the organization itself, and is used to transform information into a form usable for coordinating a company's workflow, helping employees or managers make decisions, analyze and visualize complex issues, and solve other types of problems. To do this, they use a cycle of three basic activities: input, processing and output.

IS has three basic functions in the organization of a company, which have the ability to transform information into knowledge. Are they:

- Problem solving, through equation and the proposal of solutions to support the manager of the company to act as a transformative agent;
- Knowledge production, by obtaining information that would be difficult to access by other procedures;
- Awareness raising, providing awareness of an organizational problem and developing collective awareness of its short and medium term solution.

There are some definitions of the term “management information system”, among which we can analyze the following:

- The system of people, equipment, procedures, documents and communications that collects, validates, performs operations, transforms, stores, retrieves and presents data for use in planning, budgeting, accounting, control and other management processes for various administrative purposes. Information processing systems become management information systems when their purpose transcends an orientation for transaction processing in favour of an orientation for managerial decision making;
- Organized method of providing past, present and future information related to internal operations and external intelligence service. It supports the planning, control and operation functions of a company by providing information in the appropriate time frame to assist the decision maker;
- Integrated human machine system that provides information to support the operation, management and decision making functions within the enterprise;
- A group of people or a set of data processing manuals and equipment for selecting, storing, processing and retrieving data to reduce decision-making uncertainty by

providing information to executives on time, so that they can use them in the most efficient way;

- System for the collection, storage, retrieval and processing of information used or desired by one or more executives in the performance of their activities;
- consists of at least one person of a certain psychological type who is faced with a problem in some organizational context for which it needs evidence to come up with a solution (e.g. select some course of action) and the evidence becomes available to it through some form of presentation;
- Organized method for providing the executive with past, present and future information about the company's internal operation and environment. Supports a company's control and operation planning functions by providing uniform information to assist decision making;
- combination of people, facilities, technology, environment, procedure and controls with which to maintain essential communication channels, process certain typical transaction routines, alert executives to the significance of internal and external events, and provide a basis for smart decision making.

Competitive Intelligence Systems

The strategic vision is the starting point for the company's transformational leap and, consequently, for its survival, that is, the vision is the result of managers' creativity in perceiving and analyzing the external environment.

Competitive information represents the basic input for companies to obtain competitive advantages, as it provides elements on the configuration of market forces and trends, that is, companies must develop mechanisms research and search for information considered critical, not only those that provide subsidies for their operational functioning, but also those that help them to better position them strategically.

The transformation of corporate data into competitive intelligence is of paramount importance to managers, and this is due to the division of decision support systems into model-driven systems based on models, theoretical and data analysis and aggregation capacity in statistics and historical and; in data-oriented systems that compute totals, averages and distributions from different perspectives, giving varying elements for the decision maker's interpretation.

Thus, there is the advance in the areas of networks and databases, with great interest in data warehouse, which reflects the growing importance of data-driven decision support systems.

To have a competitive intelligence system, it is necessary to create and maintain a database, and the information can be acquired through the following informational resources: Internet, security services clipping, media kit, financial sources, government sources, online database consultation, information workshop and internal networking.

The Competitive Intelligence process has its origin in the methods used by governmental intelligence agencies, which basically aimed to identify and evaluate information related to National Defense. These tools were adapted to the business reality and the new world order, and the techniques used were incorporated into this information process:

- Information Science, especially regarding formal information management;
- Information Technology, with emphasis on its network and information management tools and data mining tools;
- Management represented by its strategy, marketing and management areas.

These factors presented means that competitive intelligence systems are being considered as a further step in the development of quality and productivity programs.

If consumer-driven production is not enough to ensure a company's success, monitoring competition and new technologies is of critical importance for the company to identify threats and anticipate opportunities to gain a favourable competitive position.

Therefore, it is understood that Competitive Intelligence acts as radar for the company, providing it with the knowledge of opportunities and threats identified in the environment, which may inform its decision making, aiming at gaining competitive advantage.

In this way Competitive Intelligence can be used with the following functions in the organization: as a tool for managing technological innovation; as a tool for decision making; and as a way of adding value to the information function.

Building Organization Market Intelligence

In order to address the risks that competitiveness poses, companies need new guidance tools to help them identify and predict the constantly evolving environment. These instruments include methods of organizing, synthesizing and foreseeing

information to support their actions, thereby enabling them to be better able to cope with competition and market disruption.

The area of Competitive Intelligence, although it has acquired new contributions, methods and contributions, particularly provided by developments in the areas of Information Systems, Strategic Planning and Informatics, does not represent a totally untapped field of knowledge.

On the contrary, on information, vital input for Competitive Intelligence, much has been considered and developed both academically and in the effective practice of organizations.

Some internal data sources that deserve attention for building the organization's market intelligence, highlighting sales volumes, where the data are due to:

- Seller; Branch;
- Distribution channel;
- Form of financing;
- Product line;
- Number of salespeople,
- salespeople dedicated to each product line;
- Fixed and variable parts of the sellers commission;
- Qualification of the sales team;
- Stock level;
- Investments in advertising, promotion, events, etc .;
- Contract cancellation level;
- New customers;
- Renewal of old contracts;
- Financial profitability of each product line.

The maintenance of competitive advantages by companies requires analysis of the internal components of the organizational environment and the external components, formed by the macro-environment that affects business.

External data that will help the executive make decisions on market behaviour can be obtained through:

- Associations - set goals through the use of data provided by associations;
- Governing bodies as a source of data - in this particular case, data is collected to improve and meet the needs of the population to which it belongs;
- Government regulatory bodies - these are data provided on incentives and economic activity legislation, where statistics show market trends;
- Private research institute with consortium research - data produced on demand from the market;
- Information agency - data made available on the movement of organizational strategies in the administrative, financial and credit areas of companies;
- Internet, intranet and extranet - data made available on the web;
- Market research - data made available through direct consultation with the end customer of the product;
- Database - Data acquired through the purchase of databases from specialized companies, both in the public and private areas.

Three fundamental conditions must be met to define competitive advantage:

- The first notes that the advantage is the integration of the company's component sources, position and performance results.
- The second is that the concept of advantage lies in a superior ability, in the availability of resources that are revealed through the competitiveness of the product in the market. A vantage point can be beneficial only when it offers benefits that are perceived and valued by the customer that are difficult for the competitor to offer;
- The third identifies the products and markets for which the company is truly capable of operating; this advantage arises from the value the company can create and what is perceived by the customer. In the latter, competitive information is a key element.

Information systems

Companies often do not give full importance to the fact that managing an information systems department cannot be done in the same way as managing a sales, marketing, finance or other department.

An information system (IS) can be defined as: “a set of interrelated components working together to collect, retrieve, process, store and distribute information to

facilitate planning, control , coordination, analysis and decision making in companies and other organizations. ”

The temporal, technological and human resources characteristics differ significantly from each other, but these changes only occurred from the 90's, where the computer science was essentially linked to a computer center, and it was managed through a service provider or internally through the organization's own structure.

It was from the 1990s onwards, and especially at the end of that decade, that information system departments became a definite part of their own organizational structure and were increasingly considered as a value-adding element for companies.

This radical shift in companies' strategic approach to information system departments forces professionals in this area to be increasingly prepared to respond effectively to new supporters.

Types of Information Systems

An information system must give qualities to business information, as well as filter it by decision levels, that is, subdivide them into levels according to the functional hierarchical levels that will use them and, at the lower levels, to make them better. condensate on other information to the levels above, and so on up to the highest decision-making level, which should receive the information with a summary for strategic decisions.

The Management Information System is a process of transformation of un-compiled elements, for the formation of data, where they will have information capable of subsidizing all departments of a company for various administrative purposes aimed at the managerial decision making process is organized with appropriate past, present and future information of little uncertainty for decision makers.

An information system that expresses a fundamental conceptual structure depends on human resources (end users and IS specialists), hardware (machines and media), software (programs and procedures), data (databases and knowledge bases) and networks (communications media and network support) to perform input, processing, production, storage and control activities that convert data resources into information products.

The formation of open systems provides greater connectivity, ie, increases the ability of networked computers and other devices to easily access and communicate with each other and share information.

An open systems architecture also provides a high degree of network interoperability as it allows many different end-user applications to be realized using the diverse modalities of computer systems, software packages and databases provided by various interconnected networks.

Components of an Information System

Data and processing generate information, that a computer-based information system uses computer technology to perform part of the processing functions of an information system and also some of the input and output functions.

An information system is an integral part of an organization and is a product of three components: technology, organizations and people, where:

- Organizations - Organizations form information systems in a number of obvious ways. Companies are formal organizations. Organizations are hierarchical and structured. Each organization has a specific culture, or core assumptions, values, and way of doing things that have been accepted by most members of the company. Organizations need to build systems to solve problems created by internal and external factors;
- People - People use information from computer-based systems in their work, integrating it into their work environment. They are required to enter data into the system so that the computer can read it. Employees need training to use information systems. The user interface or those parts of an information system with which people must interact has a major influence on employee efficiency and productivity;
- Technology - Technology is the means by which data is transformed and organized for people's use. An information system can be a manual system, using only pencil and paper. Computers have replaced manual processing technology and can execute millions and even hundreds of millions of instructions per second.

An information system has resources from Information Systems. In the basic model of S, I has 5 main features: people, hardware, software, data, and networks.

- Human Resources - People are required for all information systems, including end users and IS specialists.
- Hardware Resources - all physical devices in equipment used for information processing.
- Software Resources - all sets of operating instructions called programs, designed to direct and control hardware, and instruction sets for processing information requested by people, called a procedure.

- Data Resources - More than raw materials are actually a valuable organizational resource that must be effectively managed to benefit all end users of an organization.
- Network Resources - These are telecommunications networks, such as the Internet, intranets, and extranets, which are essential to the successful operation of all companies.

Thus, companies are being able to use the IS is an important activity to characterize the success of the system and ensure its continued use, because only with proper evaluation is possible to determine whether or not the investment made in the IS has been properly recovered.

Thus, IS assessment is becoming an ever-increasing constant in organizations adopting a quality-oriented approach, using them as tools to provide and measure the quality of their services to their customers.

In the social system, there is the minimization of friction generated by the shock between the elements that move to compose it. These are attracted from the imposition of certain energies and the responsibility of the management subsystem of that organization.

But there is a risk that this system will disappear, that is, it is the function of reversing this ability to attract the elements, often triggered without the management subsystem noticing the tendency presented by the historical set of contents of the variables that represent these frictions, and should maintain content of these variables under control.

And this is obtained through the following identifications:

- The most representative variables of each event (indicator units of measure);
- The content values, allowed for each of the variables (number of units);
- Process activities that must be done to respect these values;
- The collection points of the contents of these variables after the execution of the process activities;
- Mechanisms for the perception of possible trends, and
- How to act if any tendency is observed.

Local and global telecommunication networks are being converted to digital transmission technologies, which provide information, e.g.:

(1) Significantly higher transmission speeds,

(2) the movement of larger amounts of information (3) greater economy and; (4) much lower margin of error than analog systems. In addition, digital technologies allow telecommunications networks to carry multiple types of communications (data, voice, video) over the same circuits.

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